

Endothelial Shield, A Versatile Armor: A Short Review

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Abstract

The endothelium lining of the blood vessel is a single-layer spreadsheet of epithelial cells. They form the part of the tunica intimal layer of entire blood vessels that mediate the transportation of various substances. The endothelium is a widely stretched membranous layer having variable tendency and capacity of resistance in responding against the distressful microenvironment. Endothelial cells have a tremendous retaliation capacity against the adverse metabolic environment that they encounter. Endothelial cells can show cell proliferation and play a role in repair of lesions and its renewal damaged cells. There are several predisposing factors influencing the adverse changes in the endothelium; among them hypoxia, dyslipidaemia, insulin resistance, hyperhomocysteinemia, nutrition deficiency, obesity, deep vein thrombosis, genetic factors, etc. The osmolarity of blood and its biochemical components play a pivotal role in maintaining endothelial homeostasis. Deranged blood biochemical parameters in the long run may lead to adverse pathophysiological effects on the endothelium which in turn expressed in the form of subtle inflammatory reactions that later transform into various vascular lesions affecting the function of diversified organs or structures that play role in disease establishment. Such versatile capacity of endothelial lining in various physiological and pathological conditions will be highlighted in this review article.

Introduction

In vertebrates, the circulatory system is a prerequisite for advanced growth and development to support its functional autonomy. **(Figure:1)** Myocardium is a mesodermal derivative having two layers, one develops as myocardial musculature, another one as endothelial lining of its interior. Indeed, endothelium acts as a continuous layer that lines the rest of the vascular channels. It is believed that the primitive endothelial layer is involved in transforming the cardiac myocytes into sophisticated subtle conducting channels formed within the cardiac musculature. The endocardium also gives rise to part of the interatrial, interventricular septum, cardiac valve leaflets, endocardial cushions, lining of chorda tendineae¹, etc. The endothelial cells that line the arteries and veins are flattened cells; the edges of the cells make continuous pavement and interdigitate with each other; it is referred to by different names like endocardium which lines the inner wall of the heart, mesothelium which lines the inner wall of peritoneal cavity. The regenerative capacity of endothelial cells is considerable and as a result, defects in endothelium are repaired quickly². The heart is a strong propelling organ; blood vessels are conducting and distributing shunts between the heart and peripheral tissues and organs. The endothelium acts like a metabolic and endocrine organ having a versatile capacity to adapt to the situation which in turn regulates the vascular flow. Arterial channels will attain subtle and gradual structural changes from their proximal to distal course in the body. Vascular homeostasis refers to the adequacy of blood supply, blood pressure, distribution and effective perfusion of essential elements, supply, and drainage of waste materials from the tissues including O₂, CO₂, salts, electrolytes, etc. This process is controlled by neural, endocrine, and paracrine factors³. The concept of the vascular system was initially made with the preliminary idea, that the body has two separate circulatory channels. Later William Harvey, with his series of experiments invented the closed communicating blood vascular system having arterial venous channel⁴.

The blood vessel is made of three layers tunica intima, media, and adventitia. The endothelium is a layer that lines the inner wall of the tunica intima. It is a shield of mono-layer epithelium made of simple squamous epithelium that lines the inner wall of blood vessels and lymphatic⁵. The endothelium is a shield of epithelium that lines the inner wall of blood vessels. Later is made up of a single layer of squamous epithelium, it acts as a single layer of regulatory organs and acts as a physiological barrier between the blood and vessel wall. It is relatively thick and compact lying, having versatile character involved in blood clot formation and blood coagulation in healthy conditions. The endothelium can produce various enzymes which are involved in homeostasis⁶. Endothelial squamous cells are held through gap junctions, which is an essential component for transforming the ions from smooth muscle to endothelium⁷. Advancement in microscopy have established the architecture of the endothelial layer, its basement membrane, and its cell-to-cell connections. The electron microscope has complimented our understanding of various components of the endothelial cell and its organelles explicitly. The scientists established different types of small blood vessels known as capillaries. The first type of capillary has continuous endothelium, the second one has discontinuous endothelium, and the third variety is made of fenestrated endothelium. They evolved based on their function, these varieties of capillaries pervade specifically in a particular type of anatomical structures in the body. anatomical tissue^{8,9}. There is close structural and functional synchrony between the blood biochemicals and the endothelial wall. Long-term altered blood biochemical components in the due course of time may cause endothelial cell insults followed by subtle disruption in the tunica intimal architecture which may gradually advance towards subtle adverse changes, which play a crucial role in the pathophysiology of various disorders. The dynamic behaviour of the endothelium in physiological and pathological conditions is the basic concern in this article.

Figure: 1 Cardiovascular system with endothelial layer

Endothelial cells and its role in blood vessel formation

Endothelial dynamicity is tested through extrinsic or intrinsic stimulus or environment; for which it responds through processes like differentiation, proliferation, migration, etc. For De novo vasculogenesis, endothelium operates through its properties like invasion, mitosis, fusion, adhesion, etc. Primitive angioblast cells can transform themselves into endothelial cells. The segregation of such cells is a scaffolding that leads to the formation of vascular islands called vasculogenesis. Which results in the formation of a blood vessel in its subtle form. However, the process of preexisting angioblast cell transformation into vascular plexus is known as angiogenesis. The angiogenesis involves two important mechanisms sprout angiogenesis and intussusceptive angiogenesis. Intussusceptive angiogenesis occurs with the preexisting subtle vascular plexus which undergoes ramification leading to vascular channel extensions¹⁰. Vasculogenesis is the process of formation of blood vessels by angioblast cells. Angiogenesis is a process of the formation of minute neovascular channels or capillaries by a pre-existing vessel; it is an important event that takes place during the neoplastic growth of a tissue. this phenomenon is influenced by the chemical Thromboxane A2 a potent stimulator of endothelial cells. Angiogenesis is considered an important adverse event in the spread of cancer. Vascular endothelial growth factors (VEGF) play a role in stimulation for neovascularization through their binding receptor sites; they play a role in endothelial cell

survival, proliferation, and migration. The endothelial cell migration takes place due to some chemical or mechanical stimulus. It is one of the challenges met in taming the progression of malignancy. Hence structural integrity of the endothelial layer has paramount clinical importance in cancer spread and metastasis, and it acts as a dynamic and versatile anatomical shield guarding the endovascular lining^{11,12,13}. The sprout angiogenesis will occur in response to stimuli like chemokines, vascular growth factors like (VEGF), transcription factors like Sp1, HIF-1 α and NF- κ B^{14,15, 16}. Normally, in adults, such mechanisms will reside in a mute passion where the cells will remain in “Quiescent” state. Despite this, angiogenesis will occur in a condition like wound healing, tissue regeneration, cancer-like condition¹⁷, etc. Vascular endothelial cells play their role not only in the event of angiogenesis but also during the process of effective wound healing. Based on the biochemical stress factors released in various situations, the endothelial cell secretions dictate their own activity and influence its cells nearby through autocrine and paracrine signaling communications. It is an important property that drives the mechanism of angiogenesis and the wound-healing process mediated through vascular endothelial growth factors (VEGF)¹⁸. Vasculogenesis is a process involving the coalescence of primitive scaffoldings made of Haemangioblasts for de novo synthesis of vascular channels. Endocardium and myocardium have the same precursor cardio progenitor cells of mesodermal origin, having bipotential capabilities showing the property of plasticity. Experimental studies show that many transcription factors like ETS genes mostly influence endovascular development in fetal life. *Ets2* gene expressed in vascular endothelial cells likely plays a role in angiogenesis and endothelial regeneration. Endocardium represents the subset of endothelial distribution in the central organ of the vascular system, which is derived from precardiac progenitor cells with *Flk-1* expressions to form cardiac myocytes and endothelial cells^{19,20}.

Role of Endothelium in Physiology

Altered macroscopic and microscopic changes in the vascular endothelium play a role in a wide spectrum of diseases. Anatomically endothelium is a sheet of simple squamous epithelium; later attained a typical modification to render suitable functional support in the environment or the organ in which it exists. It exists as a dynamic lining in various other anatomical structures like the interior of the heart, liver, peritoneum, pleura, nephrons of the kidney, choroid plexus, etc. It plays an important role in paracrine, autocrine, and endocrine signaling and, the transport of many metabolites, hormones, protein molecules, etc. The smooth surface of endothelium

renders homeostatic balance against undue thrombolysis and thrombosis²¹. Several molecules will be transported across the endothelial lining like glucose, amino acids, calcium, etc. These molecules will be transported through paracellular and transcellular pathways. It acts as a part of an important endovascular barrier. The tight junction will act as a physiological barrier to help in the conservative environment in the system it guards. Endothelial cells will play a special role in defense mechanisms by producing several cytokines like IL (interleukin)-1, IL-6, etc. It also secretes coagulant factors, anticoagulant factors, growth factors, adhesion molecules, vasoactive substances, immune mediators, etc. It will also produce a chemical called Willebrand factor which is manufactured by endothelial cells that act as platelet coagulant during blood coagulation²². **(Table:1)** The probable paracrine or autocrine expression of endothelial cell surface receptor modifications may play a remarkable role in preventing arterial and venous thrombosis, and thrombolysis within the physiological limits.

The functionality of endothelium is stringently regulated by the activation of several biochemical factors or mediators. Altered regulation in the endothelial factors like NO, endothelin, Angiotensin II, Thromboxane, prostacyclin's, etc. may lead to altered tone and atherosclerotic properties of endothelium in the wall of susceptible vessels, or its long-term molecular insults may systematically be manifested in the form of altered intravascular pressure changes²³. These factors play a critical role in balancing the vascular tone; its imbalance is caused by to increased secretion of vasoconstrictors and the reduced secretion of vasodilators from the endothelium may result in hypertension. Endothelium function is regulated through the balancing effect of vasoconstrictors and vasodilators. Chronic

inflammation will lead to the formation of proinflammatory chemicals like interleukin-6 which in turn leads to enhanced formation of adhesion molecules resulting in increased cardiovascular risk. C-reactive protein is an important biomarker of vascular endothelial dysfunction involved in endothelial dysfunction²⁴. Endothelium lines the lymphatic vessels also. EC has a wide array of functions, involved in metabolic homeostasis. EC can recognise the pathogenic cells. When the endothelium is injured, its properties will undergo phenomenal transformation. EC is involved in both adaptive and innate immune responses. EC plays an important role in inflammatory response by increasing prolonged permeability may result in oedema by secreting proinflammatory markers²⁵.

Role of Endothelium in Pathophysiology

There are several predisposing factors influencing the adverse changes in the endothelium; among them obesity, dyslipidaemia, insulin resistance, hyperhomocysteinemia, undernutrition, genetic causes, smoking, hypoxia, advanced aging²⁶, etc. Long-standing and escalating progressive events of hypercholesterolemia likely induce atheromatous plaque formation affecting the arterial wall. Declining low-density lipoprotein scavenging is compromised due to improper action of macrophages, which may precipitate atherosclerotic changes²⁷. **(Table:2)**

Insulin is an anabolic hormone that helps to utilize glucose by the peripheral tissues of the body. In conditions like diabetes mellitus, the excess of circulating unutilized glucose will take the diversified pathways like glycosylation, and it affects the properties of blood components. It affects platelet aggregation by enhancing the circulating adhesion molecules²⁸. The unwholesome diet and lifestyle will lead to metabolic disequilibrium causing adverse glucose metabolism and dyslipidaemia which will lead to the formation of advanced glycosylated end products (AGEs). AGEs are potential markers of metabolic syndrome influencing the tunica intimal layer changes with adverse surface receptor modifications initiating the endothelial dysfunctions²¹.

Metabolic impairment and oxidative stress have directly proportional effects on internal vascular linings. NADPH oxidase will play an important role in ROS production through renin-angiotensin pathways, or endothelin activation. Increased undue ROS production will influence the NO production which in turn causes endothelial disequilibrium²⁹. Smoking is one of the most distracting menaces affecting the individual's health. Inhalation of many toxic chemicals in the nicotinic substances will enhance oxidative stress causing inflammatory changes in the

body which affects the endothelial layer³⁰. Among many risk factors, hyperhomocysteinemia is one of the clinical conditions that very much threatens endothelial cell function; it is a condition where the body possesses high levels of serum homocysteine. This condition may affect the microvascular system related to the heart and nervous system. Hyperhomocysteinemia could be due to hypomethylation of DNA in the endothelial cell which in turn leads to the formation of adhesion of molecules by suppressing the protein expression causing the inflammatory changes subsequently followed by endothelial cell injury³¹.

Endothelial dysfunction is one of the prime factors involved in peripheral vascular impairment. The chemicals like reduced nitric oxide bioavailability content in the endothelial cells will blunt the vasodilatation response of the peripheral vessels. Which may impend the peripheral vascularity of tissues causing gradual ischemic changes; such changes involving the important vessels of the brain tissue or the myocardial cells may result in cerebrovascular and cardiovascular accidents³². Excess of homocysteine will lead to reduced production of NO a potent vasodilator, which may make an individual prone to transient ischemic attacks 33. Elevated serum homocysteine levels also lead to non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), after some time which may further progress to Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC), a common cancer of the liver and its development and progression mainly depends on endothelium and perturbations in the angioblast cells^{34, 35, 36}.

Cardiovascular disorders are a set of conditions affecting the blood vessels or the heart proper; which is one of the leading causes of morbidity or mortality worldwide. Endothelial cell is a dynamic and versatile component. Mitochondria and endoplasmic reticulum (ER) of endothelial cell organelles play crucial roles in cellular homeostasis. An altered cellular mechanism leads to cell signal impairment, and cell lesion, which may even end in cell death. The role of mitochondria and ER is much focused on increased oxidative stress; later causing the molecular destabilization in these cell organelles resulting in atherosclerotic³⁷. Lipid peroxides, Peroxynitrite, Nitrotyrosine, Glutathione, etc. are considered important biomarkers of oxidative stress. When the antioxidant enzymes fail to scavenge the reactive oxygen species (ROS) which are obnoxious products of oxidative metabolism. Aberrant cell signaling is increased in oxidative stress followed by post-translational modifications which will affect the tissue homeostasis, later likely to impact the vascular endothelial cells resulting in declining cell signal transduction and promoting apoptotic changes³⁸.

Several vasoactive mediators play a role in maintaining the vascular tone, and they respond to altered blood pressure and blood osmolarity. Endothelium attain a typical pattern to render suitable functions in the environment or organ in which it exists³⁹. Vascular tone is influenced by several biological factors, among them Nitric Oxide (NO) plays an important role; it is formed under the influence of “Nitric Oxide Synthase” enzymes which exist in 3 different forms i. e. neuronal isoform (nNO) found in nerves, inducible isoforms (iNO) found in inflammatory mediators like macrophages, and they do exist in the endothelium as endothelial nitric oxide (eNO). The probability of expression of another form of NO in other than above mentioned tissues cannot be ruled out. Endothelial nitric oxide in its free or binding state influences the release of the calcium ion and its diffusion into the cell. It is one of the important factors that play a role in maintaining the normal tone of the vessel wall. **(Table:3)** Endothelin-1 (ET-1) is a peptide protein released by endothelial cells, which acts as a strong vasoconstrictor. Endothelin-1 is produced by endothelin-converting enzyme. Farmer is expressed in different forms; various forms of its receptors are possessed by various tissues of the body resulting befitting effect. Enhanced secretion of ET-1 is influenced by several inflammatory markers like interleukins, TNF α , etc. ET-1 release is downregulated by increased concentration of nitric oxide and prostacyclin, which results in vasodilatation. The venous channels have relatively fewer receptors for ET-1 when compared to arterial channels its physiological role in venous bed seems to be less significant. The vasoconstriction and vasodilation effects are mainly influenced by the action of smooth muscles in the vessel wall⁴⁰ Certain phytochemicals like Withaferin A activate Liver X receptor and reduce angiogenesis by down-regulating ET-1 in NAFLD and HCC^{41,42}.

Prostanoids are two types, Prostacyclin (PGI₂) and Thromboxane (TXA₂); they have mutually opposite actions, and they are produced by endothelial cells. Their production is mediated by the enzyme Cyclooxygenase (COX) which plays a vital role in their balancing. Prostanoids will bind to their specific receptors on platelet cells; PGI₂ results in a declining aggregation response of platelet cells, and similarly it causes vascular smooth muscle relaxation. TXA₂ is produced by the enzyme thromboxane synthase; through its binding site receptors, it causes the aggregation of platelets, and it also results in increasing the calcium influx into the vascular smooth muscle bringing the vasoconstrictive effect⁴³. The physiological homeostasis of these compounds is very important from the point of tissue perfusion in preventing cardiovascular diseases and cerebrovascular diseases. High levels of undue circulating macronutrient molecules play an important role in impaired vascular endothelial response followed by gradually increasing insulin sensitivity. Probably which may be involved in microvasculopathy causing a reduction in peripheral blood flow, which is an important threat for nonhealing ulcers commonly seen in chronic diabetics⁴⁴.

The blood and blood biochemical constitute health state indicators. Infection-free state, sound immunity buildup, controlled BP, etc. have a great impact on ED cell lining⁴⁵. Among the several risk factors referred to earlier, the deficiency of Vitamin D stands distinctly. It is a type of secosteroids; the biological effect of Vitamin D depends on the availability of VDR (vitamin D receptor). Vitamin D deficiency affects the vascular tone and enhances calcification changes in the vessel wall. The interplay between VDR and nitric oxide production which in turn affects the vascular tone⁴⁶. The extra skeletal effect of Vitamin D mainly involves cardiovascular, and immune systems. Vitamin D deficiency can happen due to causes like deranged metabolism, deficiency in cutaneous synthesis, improper absorption, drug-drug interactions, genetic defects, etc. Sufficiency of Vitamin D shown to reduce cardiovascular risk by increasing glucose metabolism by enhancing cell sensitivity. In contrast, Vitamin D deficiency is attributed to endothelial dysfunction followed by an increased risk of atherosclerotic changes which accounts for increased cardiovascular disease risk⁴⁷. In contrast, Vitamin D and Vitamin D mimic phytochemical analog Quercetin inhibits breast cancer-induced liver inflammation and fibrosis by suppressing tumour-induced angiogenesis⁴⁸.

Structural, functional, and mechanical remodelling of peripheral arterial channels will affect the blood flow which in turn is reflected in the form of a gradual increase in intravascular pressure clinically noted as hypertension. Endothelium-mediated vascular relaxation impairment is one of the strong facilitators of hypertension⁴⁹. Ameliorating the endothelial cell resistance against undue vasoconstriction is one of the targets in the pharmaco-therapeutic approaches inducing effective tissue perfusion. Delivery of therapeutic drugs in the form of nanoparticles is the most anticipated treatment strategy. Its clinical use in the form of antihypertensive, lipid-lowering, and antidiabetic agents has potential novel therapeutic implications in targeting endothelial⁵⁰. Vascular comorbidity may manifest due to constant vascular endothelial insults followed by its dysfunction. The condition, of hypertension is very much influenced by the tone of the vasculature. Increased peripheral arterial resistance may be associated with symptoms of hypertension. Several compounds mediate the contraction and relaxation of vascular smooth muscle. Increased vascular myogenic tone will lead to increased peripheral vascular resistance. Inflammatory changes in the endothelial cell may likely precipitate peripheral vascular resistance remodelling. Hence often such conditions as hypertension may manifest with or without atherosclerotic changes⁴⁹.

Endothelium-mediated vascular relaxation impairment is one of the strong facilitators of hypertensive disorders. Ameliorating the endothelial cell resistance against undue vasoconstriction-causing chemicals is one of the targets in the pharmaco-therapeutic approaches inducing effective tissue perfusion⁵¹. It may also involve lifestyle modification, diet, and eustress for the complimentary benefits. The long-term consequence of endothelial dysfunction may result in inflammation of endothelial cells resulting in loss of cell integrity which subsequently alters the vessel wall⁵². Altered vascular tone modification could be an initial sign of its dysfunction, it may gradually influence the tissue perfusion. Prolonged undue stress on the endothelium gives rise to irreversible changes, leading to loss of integrity and adhesion of endotheliocytes may result in hampered tissue perfusion. Often detached endothelial cells are known as “endothelial cell microparticles” which start circulating in the system. They act as important markers of cardiovascular risk having much clinical significance⁵¹. Endothelial (ED) cell microenvironment is an important prerequisite for alarming immune response. ED cells are highly versatile in their action, playing roles in immune trafficking, immune stimulation, and immune inhibition. The local invasion of tissues with bacteria will be dealt with through innate immune mechanisms. Though ED they are not directly involved in immune defense and immune surveillance, they can mediate by recruiting

the immune competent cells by establishing the functional relationship between host and intruder. The invasion of the system with an antigen will aptly be responded by the endothelial cells by upregulating the immune markers which are driven through an adaptive immune response. Some of the chemicals released by the endothelial cell will help in creating the chemical gradient which invites the T-cell influx. Inhibition of certain endothelial immune markers like cytokines will safeguard against the undue inflammatory effect on the corneal tissue illustrating its inhibitory action⁵³.

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Conclusions: Endothelium is not a mere anatomical entity; in fact, it acts as a most sensitive dynamic, and versatile organ having a high adaptive capacity that drives several physiological events. Endothelium may be impacted by long-term physiological disequilibrium between the amount of undue circulatory metabolites, biochemical factors, and macro or macronutrients. Later may induce inflammatory reactions resulting in intravascular lesions affecting endothelial cell homeostasis. Hence endurance of endothelium is a robust anatomical support that plays a pivotal role in maintaining body homeostasis by preventing undue perturbations resulting in various conditions involving the process of simple wound healing to metastatic spread of malignancy. Hence it is not just an anatomical barrier but acts as an armour of the whole vascular system. Hence its physiological stance is vital in the maintenance of endovascular equilibrium and in the prevention of various disorders.

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